

UTILIZING SIX SIGMA METHODS FOR STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The majority of clinical laboratories today operate in an unfavorable economic climate. Budgets for laboratories are very strict. Employees are overworked and have little time for original problem-solving or system improvement thinking. Supervisors have too many responsibilities. The amount of money made per unit of effort is still declining. In the meantime, overhead related to regulatory obligations keeps rising. It's possible that clinical laboratories lack the funding necessary to undertake the large system re-engineering investments necessary to achieve meaningful quality improvement. These investments could result in orders of magnitude improvements in quality, possibly bringing clinical laboratories' defect rate down to levels comparable to those of other industries. Studies on healthcare are using statistical reasoning and techniques like Six Sigma more frequently these days. Six Sigma is a very methodical way to decision-making that aids in concentrating on enhancing procedures to get them as close to ideal as feasible. This is very beneficial in a situation where errors can have fatal consequences. This, however, is restricted to advancements in hospital management, but a clinical setting has untapped potential beyond cycle durations. This paper examines the error function and the cumulative distribution function of the Gaussian curve to demonstrate how Six Sigma guarantees almost perfect processes. Thirty human volunteers participate in clinical studies where physiological parameters are monitored and histograms are created to assess the repeatability of the medical equipment utilized for the measurement process. The ultimate goal is to improve public health by using statistical science to analyze differences in medical devices.

Key Words: Six Sigma, Gaussian, Histogram, Probability, Random Variable, Cumulative distribution

Introduction

The Six Sigma methodology is predominantly linked to industrial processes, and there is frequently uncertainty over the existence of a meaningful parallel between the healthcare and industrial sectors. Today's healthcare organizations must deal with mounting pressure to lower medical error rates while also cutting expenses. Six Sigma is a methodology that has proven to be beneficial to the healthcare sector by setting a high bar for acceptable quality while maintaining a laser-like focus on the bottom line. It emphasizes evaluating, improving, and reporting clinical outcomes and moves beyond "continuous improvement" programmes to precise, quantifiable targets. Six Sigma is frequently applied in the healthcare industry with the goal of reducing or eliminating errors, delays, recurrent encounters, and improper procedures. It has resulted in lower rates of medical errors, better clinical outcomes, higher cost savings, and more organizational support for quality efforts.

Statistical analysis using Six Sigma methodology is a methodical way to enhance processes and lower errors or faults in a variety of sectors. Six Sigma is a data-driven methodology that concentrates on process measurement and analysis to pinpoint areas that could require improvement.

1. Define: Clearly defining the issue or procedure that needs to be improved is the first stage in any Six Sigma project. This entails establishing clear project goals and objectives.
2. Measure: To create a baseline for the performance of the existing process, data is gathered and measured at this step. Control charts, histograms, and process capability analysis are just a few of the statistical tools and methods that are employed in data collection.
3. Analyse: After information is gathered, it is examined to determine the underlying reasons of any flaws or mistakes in the procedure. To identify the causes of variation and faults, statistical techniques such as regression analysis, hypothesis testing, and design of experiments are frequently employed.
4. Improve: During this stage, remedies to the issues found are created and put into practise. Process redesign, modifications to operating procedures, or other corrective measures are examples of improvement techniques.

5. Control: To maintain the gains and stop problems from recurring, control measures must be put in place after changes have been implemented. Process monitoring and control charts are two examples of statistical process control (SPC) approaches that are used to make sure the process stays within allowable bounds.

The difficulties, however, come from the fact that whereas the paths taken by manufacturers are well defined, those taken by healthcare providers rely on clinical judgments made at different points in time, which could make a thorough examination more difficult. All strategies need to have strong leadership, use algorithmic approaches to problem-solving that are entered on iterative development, and encourage individuals to participate in all facets of the system. These viewpoints suggest that instead of expecting to create systems that function flawlessly right away in the context of health care, we should construct a process of incremental improvement into them, with participation from all stakeholders. The most important thing is to have a systematic strategy in place to identify and reduce error sources rather than focusing on the quantity of errors.

In this study, we outline the six sigma industrial strategy and investigate the application of the ideas to the healthcare industry through clinical studies with thirty human volunteers for the analysis of physiological parameters such as body temperature.

Six Sigma Charity:

The phrase "Six Sigma Charity" is not commonly used or accepted in the context of the Six Sigma technique. Six Sigma is essentially a business process improvement methodology used in manufacturing, healthcare, and service sectors with the goal of decreasing faults and increasing process efficiency. Since its primary objective is to improve quality and decrease waste in the for-profit sector, it is not usually connected to philanthropic or nonprofit organizations.

Nonetheless, nonprofit and charitable organizations can adopt and use the Six Sigma methods and principles to increase their operational effectiveness, cut expenses, and improve their capacity to provide services. Other names for this idea are "Lean Six Sigma for Nonprofits" and "Six Sigma for Social Impact."

To make a bigger effect and more efficient use of their resources, nonprofits can implement the Six Sigma methodology in areas including volunteer management, programme delivery, administrative procedures, and fundraising. Nonprofits can more successfully carry out their purposes by locating and fixing inefficiencies and minimizing errors. The objectives and difficulties of the given charity organization would determine the precise applications and modifications.

A statistical technique known as Six Sigma was developed using ideas based on the typical normal Gaussian curve, as depicted in Figure 1. If we take precise measurements, practically everything will change in real time. Think about a basic measuring device, such as a one-foot-long scale. They could all seem to be exactly one foot long. However, if you use a standard measuring instrument and conduct an experiment in a Standard's laboratory, you may discover that some scales are 0.96 feet long while others are 1.06 feet long. Though the length of each scale varies slightly, they average out to be one foot long.

Gaussian or normal curves having a bell shape are used by statisticians to characterize patterns of these variations. (The mathematician who first deciphered the mathematics of variation in the early 1800s was Carl Frederick Gauss.) The pattern represented by the bell-shaped curve is attained if the things being measured vary continuously. Two standard deviations contain 68.26% of the variation. One standard deviation is represented by the Greek letter sigma (σ) in statistics. Six standard deviations contain 99.73% of all deviations. Three sigma are displayed to the right of the mean in Fig. 1. Suppose we added three more sigma and divided the 0.13% of the curve on the right. Stated differently, Six Sigma would exist to the right of the mean and to a very limited extent beyond it. We could actually cover 99.99966% of the variation and only find 3.4 cases out of a million that need to be excluded.

Fig.1: The Gaussian normal curve with a bell shape

Tables and formulas are used in Six Sigma initiatives to calculate sigma. All you have to keep in mind is that we want to define what a defect is, and then we want to design a process that is so consistent that, out of a million occurrences of the process, only 3.4 flaws will occur. Since most real-world events are random and may be described by statistics from a bell-shaped normal distribution, the Gaussian curve is utilized in analysis. Gaussian random variables are random variables with Gaussian probability density distributions.

A Gaussian random variable Y with mean μ_Y , standard deviation σ_Y and variance σ_Y^2 has a probability density function $f(Y)$ given by (1)

$$f(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_y} e^{\left[-\frac{1}{2\sigma_y^2}(y-\mu_y)^2\right]} \quad \text{for } -\infty < y < \infty \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Analyzing the statistics of 6σ , where σ is the standard deviation of the normal curve from the mean value ' μ' ' is made easier with the aid of the appropriate cumulative distribution function $F(y)$ of the normal distribution curve provided by "(2)".

$$F(y) = P(Y \leq y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \int_{-\infty}^y e^{\left[-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}(\omega-\mu)^2\right]} d\omega \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

In "(2)" uses ' ω ' a dummy variable, to calculate $F(y)$. Since the integral in question cannot be defined in terms of basic functions, it is difficult to evaluate. However, it is made simpler by the use of mathematically tabulated values and the principles of the error function; otherwise, it would be a laborious effort.

Error Function:

The error function, often denoted as " $\text{erf}(y)$ " is a mathematical function that is closely related to the normal distribution curve (also known as the Gaussian distribution). The error function describes the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of a standard normal distribution (mean = 0, standard deviation = 1).

The error function is defined as follows:

$$\text{erf}(y) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^y e^{-t^2} dt$$

In this formula:

y - is the upper limit of integration.

e - represents the base of the natural logarithm.

t - is the variable of integration.

The integral from 0 to y calculates the area under the standard normal distribution curve up to the point y .

The error function is used in various fields, including statistics and engineering, to calculate probabilities and solve problems related to normal distributions. It is particularly useful for finding the probability that a random variable following a standard normal distribution falls within a certain range. The error function is often used in conjunction with the complementary error function (denoted as $\text{erfc}(y)$) to solve problems related to the tails of the normal distribution curve. The complementary error function is defined as:

$$\text{erfc}(y) = 1 - \text{erf}(y)$$

In practical applications, tables or computer software are often used to look up values of the error function and its complementary function to perform calculations related to normal distributions.

The error function and the normal distribution are closely related, and the error function helps us describe and quantify the probabilities associated with various values of a normally distributed random variable.

Error function for a random variable ' v ' is written as $\text{erf}(v)$ and is defined using "(3)".

$$\text{erf}(v) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^v e^{(-z)^2} dz \quad \text{--- (3)}$$

In "(3)," ' z ' is likewise a random variable. With a few straightforward manipulations, the cumulative distribution function provided by "(2)" can be described in terms of error functions in "(4)," which is derived by rewriting "(2)."

$$F(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{[-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}(\omega-\mu)^2]} d\omega - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \int_y^{\infty} e^{[-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}(\omega-\mu)^2]} d\omega \quad \text{--- (4)}$$

The integral assessed from $-\infty$ to ∞ for the probability density function (p.d.f) of $f(y)$ is the first integral on the right side of "(4)". By the p.d.f. property:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y) dy = 1 \quad \text{--- (5)}$$

Using "(5)", we obtain a simplified version of "(4)" as below.

$$F(y) = 1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \int_y^{\infty} e^{[-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}(\omega-\mu)^2]} d\omega \quad \text{--- (6)}$$

Let

$$\psi = \frac{\omega - \mu}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \Rightarrow d\psi = \frac{d\omega}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \quad \text{----- (7)}$$

Replacing set of equations from “(7)” into “(6)” we obtain modified $f(y)$ as below:

$$F(y) = 1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \int_{\frac{\omega-\mu}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}}^{\infty} e^{-\psi^2} \sqrt{2} d\omega$$

or

$$F(y) = 1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_{\frac{\omega-\mu}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}}^{\infty} e^{-\psi^2} d\omega \quad \text{----- (8)}$$

The complementary error function denoted as $\text{erfc}(v)$, is related to the error function by the equation given below

$$\text{erfc}(v) = 1 - \text{erf}(v)$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{erfc}(v) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^v e^{-z^2} dz \quad \text{----- (9)}$$

Modifying “(8)” in terms of $\text{erfc}(v)$ by using “(9)” we have

$$F(y) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_{\frac{\omega-\mu}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}}^{\infty} e^{-\psi^2} d\omega \right]$$

$$F(y) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left[\frac{y - \mu}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right] \quad \text{----- (10)}$$

$$F(y) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \text{erf} \left[\frac{y - \mu}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right] \quad \text{----- (11)}$$

In general, for a mean, $\mu = 0$, the cumulative distribution function can be denoted as below:

$$F(y) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \text{erf} \left[\frac{y}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right] \quad \text{----- (12)}$$

The probability of a random experiment with a Gaussian distribution can be computed with the use of the error function and the complementary error function. "(13)" gives the chance that a random variable y is not more than $(k\sigma_y)$ away from a mean value μ_y , where k is a constant.

$$P(\mu_y - k\sigma_y \leq Y \leq \mu_y + k\sigma_y) = \int_{\mu_y - k\sigma_y}^{\mu_y + k\sigma_y} f(y)dy \quad \text{--- (13)}$$

Or

R.H.S

$$= F(\mu_y + k\sigma_y) - F(\mu_y - k\sigma_y)$$

In terms of error function, the above equation can be written as

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}} \right) - \operatorname{erf} \left(-\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \right]$$

The property for error function says ' $\operatorname{erf}(v) = -\operatorname{erf}(-v)$ ' Using this fact in the above equation we have the following:

$$P(\mu_y - k\sigma_y \leq Y \leq \mu_y + k\sigma_y) = \operatorname{erf} \left[\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}} \right] \quad \text{--- (14)}$$

For $k = 3$, we have the probability as

$$P(\mu_y - 3\sigma_y \leq Y \leq \mu_y + 3\sigma_y) = \operatorname{erf} \left[\frac{3}{\sqrt{2}} \right] = 0.9970 \quad \text{--- (15)}$$

Thus, using tabulated error function values, one can readily calculate probabilities for different variance values [10]. Details of the error function for various k values are shown in Table I, which is

Table I: Probability for Different K values

S.No.	k	$P(\mu_y - 3\sigma_y \leq Y \leq \mu_y + 3\sigma_y)$
1	0.50	0.3830
2	1.00	0.6830
3	1.50	0.8660
4	2.00	0.9550
5	2.50	0.9880
6	3.00	0.9970
7	3.50	0.99950
8	4.00	0.999940

Calculated from the "Area under the Normal (Gaussian) Curve," tabulated data that may be found in books on higher engineering mathematics with ease [1].

Hence, it is easy to confirm that a 6-sigma variance has a chance of 0.997; 99.99966% of the deviation is covered, and the notion of Six Sigma is excluded in just 3.4 out of every million cases.

Six Sigma Methodology:

Six Sigma is a systematic and data-driven methodology for process improvement and quality management. It was originally developed by Motorola in the 1980s and has since been widely adopted by organizations across various industries. The primary goal of Six Sigma is to reduce defects, improve processes, and enhance the quality of products and services. The term "Six Sigma" refers to a level of quality where the probability of a defect occurring is extremely low, with approximately 3.4 defects per million opportunities (or 99.9997% defect-free).

The four phases of the approach that Six Sigma uses are described below [4, 6, 13, 14]:

Measure: Defects in the process that affect important customer requirements are found and gathered. Thirty human volunteers are used to monitor physiological parameters. For every topic, two distinct Digital Thermometers of the same kind are used to measure the temperature, which

is entered into Table II. The temperature readings (in degrees Fahrenheit) from two separate thermometers are T1 and T2.

Analyze: Variations are computed for every subject for each calculations are made using the thermometer reading and the variance. The difference in degrees Fahrenheit between T1 and T2 is T3. The formulas in "(16)" and the Z table in Table III are used to estimate the percentage of rejection Z, the defect measurement error value, is derived from common Six Sigma calculation methodologies to create the Z table. The upper specification limit is known as *USL*. The mean is represented by $\bar{Y}$, and the standard deviation by σ .

$$Z = \left(\frac{USL - \bar{Y}}{\sigma} \right) \quad \text{----- (16)}$$

Enhance: These variables' effects are measured, and acceptable ranges one, two, three, etc., are established. The temperature difference is shown by a histogram, and the deviation from the Gaussian curve obtained with Mini Tab is then computed. Mini Tab is the application software used for statistical analysis using Six Sigma techniques.

Control: Statistical process control tools are used to monitor the performance of the process. The quality of the medical equipment can be raised by calibrating the results.

Table II: Temperature readings expressed in degrees Fahrenheit

S.No.	T1 (Degree F)	T2 (Degree F)	T3 (Difference Degree F)
1	103.1	102.9	0.2
2	103.0	102.8	0.2
3	102.9	102.5	0.4
4	102.7	102.4	0.3
5	102.6	102.3	0.3
6	102.6	102.2	0.4
7	102.4	102.1	0.3
8	102.4	102.2	0.2
9	102.1	102.1	0
10	102.1	101.9	0.2
11	102.0	102.3	0.3
12	101.9	101.6	0.3
13	101.8	101.6	0.2
14	101.6	101.4	0.2
15	101.1	100.8	0.3
16	100.9	100.7	0.2
17	100.9	100.7	0.2
18	100.8	100.3	0.5
19	100.7	100.4	0.3
20	100.7	100.2	0.5
21	100.6	100.0	0.6
22	100.3	100.2	0.1
23	100.1	99.8	0.3
24	99.6	99.4	0.2
25	99.3	99.2	0.1
26	99.4	98.8	0.6
27	99.1	98.2	0.9
28	98.5	98.3	0.2
29	98.5	98.3	0.2
30	98.4	98.3	0.1

Table III: Z Table

S.No.	z	Rejection
1	0-0.50	50-31%
2	0.60-1.00	27-16%
3	1.10-1.50	13-6.50%
4	1.60-2.00	5.5-2.2%
5	2.10-2.50	17000-6200 ppm
6	2.60-3.00	4700-1350 ppm
7	3.10-3.50	970-230 ppm
8	<3.5	<230 ppm

Figure 2 shows the histogram plot of the temperature variation measured with two thermometers of the same brand. It is evident that the average of the thirty recordings is 0.21. The computed standard deviation is 0.09595. Utilizing "(16)" and presuming $USL = 0.3$, $Z = 3.12$ was computed. The matching rejection percentage, as determined by the standard Z-table, is 970 ppm.

Fig. 2: The Histogram plot displays the variation in temperature readings taken from two identically made thermometers.

The only basis for the observations and analysis is a comparison of the two thermometers' respective temperature readings. The deviation has not been compared to any established, calibrated standard instrument from a recognized university. The calculation of the defect rates was done with the presumption that $USL=0.3$. It is also possible to examine the fault rates for different USL values.

Variance analysis of this kind can be performed on a wide range of clinical tools and procedures. The findings may indicate areas where the procedure could be clearly improved, which could result in improved clinical analysis and fewer therapy iterations. All of this creates a pathway for cost savings and waste minimization.

Conclusions:

Applying Six Sigma techniques to the statistical analysis of human physiological parameters can be a valuable approach, especially in healthcare and medical research. Six Sigma can help identify areas of improvement, reduce errors, and enhance the quality of healthcare delivery.

Medical devices should be accurate and easy to use, as even little differences in measurements can result in incorrect results when used in clinical analysis. There can always be a discrepancy between the supply and demand for competent managers, physicians, and technicians; therefore, it is preferable to identify the reasons behind deviations and set up dependable procedures and final goods. This would guarantee the widespread establishment and accessibility of standard healthcare.

The testing and recording process as a whole does not seem to be greatly improved by previous quality assurance initiatives. Medical equipment performance can be improved methodically with the use of quality system solutions for performance improvement like Six Sigma, which would also automatically guarantee better, quicker, and less expensive treatments. Clinical research should benefit from the application of Six Sigma in terms of standardization and advancements in medical equipment. This provides a wide range of applications for statistical methods such as Six Sigma and their offshoot concepts, such as lean. These include enhancing patient satisfaction through better medical administration, as well as having an effect on trustworthy clinical analysis and the general standard of healthcare.

It's important to involve healthcare professionals, data analysts, and process improvement experts in this Six Sigma approach to ensure that improvements are both effective and sustainable. By applying Six Sigma techniques to the analysis of human physiological parameters, healthcare organizations can enhance the quality of care, reduce errors, and improve patient outcomes.

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